

UPLB READY BOARD GAME: GAMIFIED DISASTER PREPAREDNESS USING MECHANICS-DYNAMICS-AESTHETICS FRAMEWORK

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ABSTRACT

This paper critically examines the effectiveness of a gamified disaster preparedness workshop conducted at the University of the Philippines Los Baños (UPLB) campus. The board game, created by the author, was inspired by the Metro Manila Development Authority (MMDA) first responder training module known as 'Earthquake and Landslide Search and Rescue Orientation Course' or 'ELSAROC'. The purpose of the board game is to enable the participants to manage an incident team in an earthquake and landslide scenario to exercise their critical thinking. In this study, responses were gathered from a total of sixty-eight (68) participants, including faculty, researchers, administrative staff, and students. The study utilized the Mechanics-Dynamics-Aesthetics (MDA) framework introduced by Hunicke, LeBlanc, and Zubek. Overall, the gamified workshop received high remarks and was deemed beneficial. The findings of this study offer valuable insights for academic comparison between traditional discussion and gamified workshops. The board game proved to be an effective, experiential, and enjoyable method for teaching disaster preparedness.

Keywords: *Board Game, Disaster Preparedness, Gamified*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippines has never been new to facing risks of emergencies and disasters, and this includes the natural dread that is brought by earthquakes and landslides, wherein

anticipation is never near nor clear, but preparedness will equip the people with better chances to survive and be free or less in injuries and casualties. Such preparedness has been vitally significant as a potential factor for means of prevention in hindering the count of damages, afflictions, and mortalities. With the numerous incidents of evident destruction that the country has faced with the countless earthquakes with varying magnitudes and intensities that the Filipinos have experienced, the government officials from the national to the local in particular have already been engaging in training and educating individuals in disaster preparedness (Domingo & Manejar, 2018).

In that context, the need to explore the effectiveness of the different methods and delivery of cascading disaster education into training, workshops, and other learning activities is a critical issue that needs validation. In essence, how effective are each individual's learning process and retention to internalize the whole knowledge acquired from different learning activities. This paper critically examines the effectiveness of a gamified workshop using a board game.

This research takes a particular interest in analyzing the newly developed board game the author developed. The following section provides an overview of the research problems, research objectives, review of related literature, and methodology to introduce the game-initiated learning from the gamified workshop and analyze the respondent's feedbacks.

Research Problem

Since the common delivery of cascading is through sit-down lectures, this time a gamified workshop will be tested to determine which training method is more effective in disaster preparedness. Thus, in this regard, the research question can be stated as follows:

1. What is the level of the acceptability of the respondents towards the concept of gamification?
2. What are the perceptions of the respondents after testing the board game?
3. How effective is the gamified workshop compared with the traditional discussion in the context of learning objectives?

Research Objectives

This study aims to analyze the effectiveness of the gamified workshop using board game. The following are the specific objectives:

1. To determine the respondent's assessment of the concept of gamification.
2. To understand the perceptions of the players or respondents after testing the board game.
3. To come up with recommendations based on the findings of this study in the context of learning objectives.

Significance of the Study

By studying disaster preparedness, one can understand how these phenomena work, including the associated risks and their impacts. The board game created in this study, aims to enhance retention and lasting learning experiences. This thorough understanding of the importance of validation, the gap and deficiency will be addressed.

Limitation of the Study

This study focuses solely on one learning institution, which is UPLB, as a case study. The research was conducted at a specific study site in the Municipality of Los Baños, in the province of Laguna. Therefore, additional research in other locations and institutions is necessary to broaden the findings.

Game-Based Learning Insights from Various Studies

In a study conducted by Tsai et al. (2014) in Taiwan, they are innovating and utilizing game-based education to foster preparedness with the methods of “Shikakeology” and learning that are game-initiated, wherein the game simulating flood scenarios and problems, with integrated discussions to enable management during flood disaster. The study found 92% of utility among the student-respondents and can embed strategies for disaster prevention, 96% of them were also willing to retry the game, and 98% have been committed to paying more attention to issues involving disaster prevention.

Meanwhile, according to Sari and Wahyuni (2015), as their study aimed to develop the preparedness board game for natural disaster. The result of this study indicated that developed preparedness board game was worth based characteristics of students. It was concluded that learning media preparedness board game could be used in the learning process in the natural disaster material. In the game-based learning strategy, the learners are highly engaged in the learning process. Other studies suggest a significant increase in the knowledge of the students on educational intervention when subjected to game methods than in a lecture-based setting, thus, implying that the game-based educational method is better when it comes to its effectiveness than the traditional methods; hence, can be considered as an approach anew in promoting and raising awareness for the management of disaster risk (Moradian and Nazdik, 2019).

Culibar (2020) also examined the same variability of applications for disaster risk reduction in a study and focused on the mnemonic of disaster risk and a framework of serious game design in substantiating the concepts and realities of disaster risk reduction with the elements of the game. However, the findings of the study emanated challenges concerning professions in mapping and laying out the realities of disaster risk reduction in a game; hence, it is hereby recommended that a methodological approach be employed to create a common ground for both the variables, but there is already an established relation and compatibility with the profound game design framework and the concepts and realities of disaster risk reduction. In this light, it was suggested that collaboration be upheld to create storylines for the game, which will be vulnerability-inspired, with government and local capacities integrated.

In learning based on socio-scientific issues board game conducted by Cheng et al. (2020) the result indicated that after playing the game, participants knowledge and responsibility regarding water resource adaptation improved significantly. Furthermore, the findings revealed that the gap between the learning outcomes of participants with different roles in the game was not statistically significant, except in terms of students' personal willingness to act.

Hafeez (2021) compared the students learning outcomes with game-based and traditional learning strategies as a result the game-based learning strategy proved to be a highly effective learning strategy in numerous disciplines under different learning environments.

In another study conducted by Coban and Goktas (2023) focused on comparing drills, digital games, and traditional education concerning the motivation that stems from earthquake education and enabling preparedness and prevention knowledge. The findings elucidated that the student-respondents were more motivated with the traditional education than the digital game and conduct of drills, with significantly less motivation for digital games. At the same time, it has been concluded that all of the methods were able to instill learning content that encompasses real-life situations concerning protection, defense, and survival.

Theoretical Framework

In game development and studies, a game design framework allows diverse backgrounds or viewpoints to achieve a systematic coherence for different parts of a game to relate to one another (Hunicke et al., 2004). The Mechanics-Dynamics-Aesthetic or MDA framework which Hunicke, LeBlanc and Zubek introduced, is a formal approach to understanding games by breaking them into their distinct components: **mechanics** describes the particular components of the game, **dynamics** describes the run-time behavior of the mechanics acting on players inputs and each other's outputs, and **aesthetics** describes the desirable emotional responses evoked in the player as well as the interactions with the game system.

Furthermore, when working with games, it is helpful to consider both the designer's and player perspectives (Hunicke et al., 2004).

Hunicke et al., 2004

Conceptual Framework

The researcher will employ the Input-Process-Output framework to draw the final output of this study. The input process shall begin with the design, development, and rollout of the board game. In the second stage, feedback analysis is conducted, the game was refined by considering feedback taken and observations made at the end of the pilot study. The roll out of the board game was approved by no less than the Chancellor of UPLB and was evaluated by four (4) offices inside the campus.

The output is the findings of this study to present the detailed information about the experiences of respondents. Below is the structured conceptual framework.

Innovative Board Game: From Concept to Reality

The author developed a disaster learning board game focusing on its design concept and game mechanics. The game’s idea is to adopt the principle of managing an incident team in earthquake and landslide scenarios.

The board game was conceptualized using one of the first responder training facilitated by the MMDA, commonly known as the ELSAROC. A total of three (3) training sessions was conducted at UPLB, the first training in 2015, the second in March 2018, and the last training was in December 2022. These training helped shape the game’s design, making it an effective tool for disaster preparedness and enhancing critical thinking skills among participants. (please see Figure 1)

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Figure 1

Board Game Design and Mechanics

Going back to the board game concept, the pilot design was made using only cartolina paper, with cutouts of character figures made from colored paper. (please see Figure 2)

Figure 2

The author then began to write the game mechanics, which are straightforward and easy to understand. They will act as an incident commander and manage a team of responders. Each player within the designated space of the boardgame has its own gamecard of rescue team composed of a fire fighter, first aider, police, and rescuer as well as emergency rescue vehicle such as fire truck, ambulance, police patrol car and back hoe loader. In addition, they will be given each money card where they can buy a rescue personnel or vehicle.

The journey of players around the board game is subject to different disaster situation. Each player picks the scenario card from the game master. The player needs to read out loud and act accordingly to the given situation, either a player lands on a worst-case scenario or not, depending on the requirements, this a typical elimination game until a player runs out of gamecard. But there are bonus card depending on the random draw of cards which they will receive additional rescue personnel or vehicle gamecard. If one of the players runs out of gamecard, the game will continue with the remaining players until one remaining player declared the winner. (please see Figure 3)

Figure 3

Given the final lay out, it was printed on sintra board for the final design of the board game itself. (please see Figure 4)

Figure 4

Here, it was introduced and presented through a memorandum submitted to the Office of the Chancellor; luckily, it was approved. The roll-out of board game was approved by Chancellor Jose V. Camacho Jr. through the issuance of OC Memorandum No. 006 series of 2023 on January 18, 2023. (please see Figure 5)

 UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES LOS BAÑOS
Office of the Chancellor

18 January 2023

MEMORANDUM NO. 006
Series of 2023

TO : **All Vice Chancellors, Deans, Directors, Department Chairs, and Unit Heads**

SUBJECT : **Invitation to Participate in the "UPLB READY" ELSAROC Board Game and Mock Drill Exercise**

The Security and Safety Office (SSO), formerly University Police Force (UPF), under the Office of the Vice Chancellor for Community Affairs (OVCCA) is inviting representatives from your unit to participate in a game-based cascading workshop and mock drill exercise at the Obdulia F. Sison Hall (Continuing Education Center) that will run from February to June 2023.

"UPLB READY" is a program aimed at promoting disaster preparedness and encouraging the involvement of all UPLB personnel in promoting campus safety education. ELSAROC stands for Earthquake and Landslide Search and Rescue Orientation Course. The objectives of the board game and mock drill exercise are to give the participants the ability to manage an incident management team in every disaster risk scenario, especially in search and rescue operations, and experience hands-on or close-to-real collapsed structure scenarios. Both activities can be used in classes, workshops, and teambuilding sessions.

The activity is free of charge. The first 50 participants will receive one limited edition "UPLB READY" desk calendar. Please bring your food and water during the game. The slots for both sessions are limited; hence, kindly confirm your attendance by contacting the SSO – Crisis and Emergency Response Unit at telephone numbers 536-2243/2803 or via email at parquiza@up.edu.ph or knmaligalig@up.edu.ph until **15 February 2023**.

Thank you for your continued support and cooperation.

Figure 5

Prior to its official launch, the author involved his staff to assist him in the cascading activities on the campus. Several pre-tests were conducted to gather additional feedback and comments to improve the board game more convincingly and appealingly, as well as to review the narrative of the game mechanics, the design, and some of the special considerations. (please see Figure 6)

Figure 6

Initially, the board game was tested at the University Police Headquarters (now renamed Security and Safety Office or SSO). The author invited some of the SSO personnel to try the board game. They were all excited while playing the board game, and positive feedback was received.

In an article written by Matalog (2023), the board game was tested with the UPLB Gender Center (GC); given that our icon player aesthetic design has a female incident commander, wherein it passed with the assessment and the author considers the recommendation of gender equality even in a board game. (Please see Figure 7)

Figure 7

Two more rollout activities using the board game, engaging the university's student affairs of the university and our communication office for the gamified workshop. This will now become part of our learning activities in UPLB including students from UP Rural High School (UPRHS), as an alternative way of cascading disaster preparedness information wherein the typical sit-down lectures and common PowerPoint presentations will be replaced with an experiential learning and fun game. (Please see Figure 8)

Figure 8

In an article written by Marza (2023), the board game was also tested with UPLB Pahinungód, in promoting the volunteerism service program; the idea is to test the feasibility of this board game being useful in workshops, outdoor classes, and team-building sessions. (Please see Figure 9)

Figure 9

Furthermore, given the six (6) months rollout of the board game, the author received positive feedbacks; participants gained awareness and understanding of various earthquake intensities and landslides effect. In addition, players or participants of the UPLB board game will learn the fundamentals of search and rescue.

METHODOLOGY

Questionnaires were tailored and drafted accordingly for the feedback mechanism approach. In this study, a qualitative research method was used for data collection. Aside from the questionnaire, a five (5) point Likert scale response method was used where respondents can easily answer questions and state their acceptance, agreement and quality of the gamified workshop. A total of sixty-eight (68) respondents composed of faculty, researchers, administrative staff, and students, were collected through their responses.

The participants were selected through purposive sampling from the different offices, namely: GC, Office of the Vice Chancellor for Student Affairs (OVCSA), Office of Public Relations (OPR), UPRHS, and Ugnayan ng Pahinungód inside the campus. The reasons for selecting these offices and participants: first, the OVCSA and UPRHS represent the student body, and it is essential to get feedback from them as principal beneficiaries of this activity. Second, for the OPR, in the context of communication and clarity of the narratives. Third, for the GC, the office's primary mandate is to ensure gender-based equality and other feedback from the design that characterizes the male and female icons of players. Lastly, for the volunteerism service program of Ugnayan ng Pahinungód, the idea is to test the feasibility of this board game being useful in workshops, outdoor classes, and team-building sessions.

This study contained three (3) demographic and five (5) qualitative question items that directly evaluated the gamified workshop. The demographic questions for this study are job title, and office. The respondents will be rating this research questions on a scale of one (1) to five (5). The questions focus on gamified workshop, design of the board game materials, the organization and delivery of the gamified workshop, and the overall learning experience. The researcher will follow ethical standards, starting with obtaining full consent from respondents. The integrity of the research will be based on actual findings, and the researcher will conduct the research process with honesty and impartiality.

RESULTS

This study aimed to gauge the level of acceptability, perception, and effectivity of the board game. Aside from the questionnaire, a 5-point Likert scale response method was used where respondents can easily answer questions and state their acceptance, agreement, and quality of the gamified workshop.

The demographic presentation for this study, as follows:

A total of sixty-eight (68) respondents. Thirty-seven (37) are male, and thirty-one (31) are female. Three (3) are faculty, ten (10) are researchers, twenty (20) are admin staff, and thirty-five (35) are students.

Twelve (12) from the GC, twenty-four (24) from OVCSA & OPR, twenty-two (22) from UPRHS and ten (10) from Ugnayan ng Pahinungód.

Here are the following responses and their implications:

Overall rating of the quality of this gamified workshop

Most respondents rated between the scale of 4 (above average) and 5 (excellent). Only one (1) rated average. The majority of the offices rated excellent as to the overall quality of this gamified workshop. (please see table 1)

Table 1. Overall rating of the quality of this gamified workshop

Office	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Gender Center	4.67	Excellent
OVCSA & OPR	4.54	Excellent
UPRHS	4.45	Excellent
Pahinungód	4.60	Excellent
Total	4.57	Excellent

Overall rating of the design of the board game materials

Most respondents rated between the scale of 4 (good) and 5 (very good). Only one (1) rated acceptable. The OVCSA, OPR, and UPRHS rated the overall aesthetic design as very good. However, both the GC and Pahinungód rated it as good. (please see table 2)

Table 2. Overall rating of the design of the board game materials

Office	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Gender Center	4.25	Excellent
OVCSA & OPR	4.58	Excellent
UPRHS	4.55	Excellent
Pahinungód	4.30	Excellent
Total	4.42	Excellent

Overall rating of the way the gamified workshop is organized and delivered

Again, most respondents rated between the scale of 4 (good) and 5 (very good). Only one (1) rated acceptable. Again, both OVCSA, OPR and UPRHS rated the highest appreciation as outstanding concerning the overall organization and delivery of this gamified workshop. (please see table 3)

Table 3. Overall rating of the way the gamified workshop is organized and delivered

Office	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Gender Center	4.42	Excellent
OVCSA & OPR	4.50	Excellent
UPRHS	4.45	Excellent
Pahinungód	4.50	Excellent
Total	4.47	Excellent

Overall rating of the learning experience

As to overall learning experience, the majority again rated between the scale of 4 (above average) and 5 (excellent). Only one (1) rated average. UPRHS has the highest excellent rating and is followed by OVCSA and OPR. (please see table 4)

Table 4. Overall rating of the learning experience

Office	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Gender Center	4.42	Excellent
OVCSA & OPR	4.54	Excellent
UPRHS	4.59	Excellent
Pahinungód	4.50	Excellent
Total	4.51	Excellent

Table 5. Likert Scale Interval Interpretation

Scale	Interval	Verbal Interpretation (A)
1	1.00 – 1.80	Very Poor
2	1.81 – 2.60	Below Average
3	2.61 – 3.40	Average
4	3.41 – 4.20	Above Average
5	4.21 – 5.00	Excellent

Table 6. Summary of Interpretation

Scale	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Overall rating of the quality of this gamified workshop	4.57	Excellent
Overall rating of the design of the board game materials	4.42	Very Good
Overall rating of the way the gamified workshop is organized and delivered	4.47	Very Good
Overall rating of the learning experience	4.51	Excellent
Total	4.49	

Effective Experiential Learning and Fun Game

Most respondents stated that the game was exciting and fun. This indicates that the board game was relatively interesting among these individuals. A few respondents said that with the help of the board game you can now easily learn the basic information about the earthquake intensities and its possible impact.

Some respondents have reflected on their experiences as follows:

- *“Very outstanding execution; I enjoyed it.”*
- *“Overall, the game is fun and informative.”*
- *“It’s fun.”*
- *“It was fun.”*
- *“Game was fun, informative, interactive. First time to experience this way of presenting the topics.”*

- *“I love it.”*
- *“Fun.”*
- *“Overall, a fun game.”*
- *“Super engaging and insightful game.”*
- *“It was a lot of fun.”*

Contribution to Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) Principles

Respondents predominantly expressed strong agreement regarding its potential contribution to DRR principles.

Some of the respondents have reflected on their experiences as follows:

- *“The game was easy to understand and play; what's interesting is its unpredictability just like natural disasters; you don't know what cards you will get or when calamities will hit.”*
- *“I think with time playing with the cards, you would familiarize the terms of search and rescue.”*
- *“Fun way to learn about search and rescue.”*

Suggested Minor Revisions for the Board Game Scenarios

This theme touches upon potential revisions for the improvement of the board game.

Some respondents have expressed their views as follows:

- *“More modifications in the game, more scenarios.”*
- *“More interactions and scenarios.”*
- *“Good job. More responsibility for the medic scenario.”*
- *“Time limit for decision-making (15 secs), allow for resource trading among players, allow for resource trading (based on resource value) clarification for interchangeability.”*
- *“Come up with a way to conceal the answer and let the player guess what resources needed to use. In a way this will allow/test the player's critical thinking.”*
- *“We would have loved to have a wider variety of cards, maybe an expansion pack in the future?”*
- *“Consequence if chosen resources are wrong also not show the needed resources used.”*
- *“Please take note of the typos, punctuations, and other words like policeman. Also, use simpler words such as oscillates. Thank you.”*

The suggestion to revise scenarios and mechanics in the board game was beneficial.

DISCUSSION

This study aims to analyze the effectiveness of the gamified workshop using board game. The specific objectives are to determine the assessment of the concept of gamification, know the perceptions of the respondents after testing the board game and come up with recommendations based on the findings of this study to achieve the learning objectives.

According to the results, most players or respondents said the game was exciting and fun. In this respect, respondents predominantly expressed strong agreement regarding its potential contribution to DRR principles. The discussion of the responses provides valuable insights into the level of acceptability, as well as the perceptions of its potential impact on disaster training activities. These insights also shed light on the measures that can be taken to improve the board game by adding more scenarios in the game mechanics. In summary, the responses were grouped into three (3) themes: effective experiential learning and fun games, contribution to DRR principles, and future expansion of board game scenarios.

Conclusions

The responses revealed that the gamified workshop using board game was a valuable tool in capacity-building activities to learn the basics of disaster management. According to the respondents, the game was fun, informative, and interactive. It was the first time for them to experience the other way around of presenting the topics or lectures relating to disaster preparedness in general. The level of acceptability of the gamified workshop was closely related to levels of agreement on the board game potential contribution to common DRR principles. This indicates a consensus among most participants regarding the board game's significance and its potential to contribute positively to disaster preparedness. Furthermore, the respondents stated that they were pleased because the training method offered was easy to understand, and what was interesting to them was its unpredictability, just like natural disasters, you do not know what cards you will get or when calamities will hit.

Recommendations

To enhance learning outcomes from the gamified workshop using the board game, consider the following recommendations. First, expand the scenarios to include a wider variety of disaster scenarios. Second, incorporate game mechanics that require players to make decisions, in a way, this will allow or test the players critical thinking. Lastly, continuously gather and use participant feedback to refine the game for proper improvements.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This paper is authored by single individual who adheres to ethical standards. The author obtained respondents' consent while conducting this survey, clearly explained the study's purpose, and ensured the confidentiality of their identities. The author also obtained permission to take photos during the actual board game. Furthermore, there is no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of this study, and the author conducted the research analysis with integrity and neutrality.

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